

NOGUCHI MEMORIAL INSTITUTE FOR MEDICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD (NMIMR-IRB) CHILD ASSENT FORM

Introduction

My name is **Dr. Irene Ayi** and I am from the **Department of Parasitology** at **Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research**. I am conducting a research study entitled **Surveillance of Pathogens associated with Diarrhea Outbreaks in Ghana: Detection and Molecular Characterization of Diarrhea causing Parasites**. I am asking you to take part in this research study because I am trying to learn more about the germs that cause diarrhoea in children. This will take a minimum of few hours to a maximum of two days for you to participate.

General Information

If you agree to be in this study, you will be asked to provide some of the stool you pass either whilst we are still here at the hospital or tomorrow. We may also take measurements of your weight and height if we do not find them in your medical records.

Possible Benefits

Your participation in this study will help us to know if parasites are contributing to the diarrhoea you are experiencing. Your test results will be shared with the medical officer in charge. It will help medical officer to give you the appropriate treatment and to manage such diarrhoea cases very well.

Compensation

You will not be paid for participation in this study but will receive a token (biscuits and a tin of ideal milk) for the time you spend to participate in this study. This token will be given to you after you have agreed to be part of the study and the stool sample has been collected

Possible Risks and Discomforts

Only stool samples passed by you will be collected. This will not cause any harm to you. The necessary precautions will be taken at all times to ensure your safety.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Leave the Research

You can stop participating at any time if you feel uncomfortable. No one will be angry with you if you do not want to participate.

Confidentiality

Your information will be kept confidential. No one will be able to know the information we will copy from your medical records and your information will be anonymous.

Contacts for Additional Information

You may ask me any questions about this study. You can call me at any time on mobile telephone number 0243670493 or talk to me the next time you see me.

Please talk about this study with your parents before you decide whether or not to participate. I will also ask permission from your parents before you are enrolled into the study. Even if your parents say “yes” you can still decide not to participate.

VOLUNTARY AGREEMENT

By making a mark or thumb printing below, it means that you understand and know the issues concerning this research study. If you do not want to participate in this study, please do not sign this assent form. You and your parents (or caregiver) will be given a copy of this form after you have signed it.

This assent form which describes the benefits, risks and procedures for the research titled **Surveillance of Pathogens associated with Diarrhea Outbreaks in Ghana: Detection and Molecular Characterization of Diarrhea causing Parasites** has been read and or explained to me. I have been given an opportunity to have any questions about the research answered to my satisfaction. I agree to participate.

Child's Name:.....

Researcher's Name:.....

Child's Mark/Thumbprint.....

Researcher's Signature:.....

Date:

Date: